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A Study of Social Media Addiction, Moral Values, and Mental Health Among University Students

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship between social media addiction, moral value and mental health. The study was conducted on university students, from various universities of Lahore. It was hypothesized that there was a significant negative relationship between media addiction and moral value. There was a significant positive relationship between social media and mental health. There was a significant positive relationship between Age and Moral Values. Females are more likely to be more addicted to social media as compared to males. A sample of 200 students was taken through a random sampling technique. Assessment measures used in the study for measuring Social Media Addiction (Sahin, 2008), The Ethics Position Questionnaire (Hans, 1993) and Mental Health Continuum Short form (Keyes, 2012) were used to test the relationship among variables. The data was analyzed through various statistical analyses. The results of person product moment correlation analysis showed that there is a non-significant and negative relationship between social media addiction and moral value. There is a significant and positive relationship between social media and mental health. Results show that there is a likely to be a positive relationship between age and high Moral Value. Moreover, as per results both females and males are addicted to social media. Multiple Hierarchical Regression analysis was conducted to check relations between the variables. The study can help understand the underlying negative consequences of social media usage and how moral values affected by the social media addiction does and what factors affect their mental health.

Keywords: Social Media Addiction, Moral Values, Mental Health, Depression, Anxiety, Stress.

INTRODUCTION

In the modern area, social media is playing a vital role in our daily lives. There is a fundamental need in humans to belong and relate, and to communicate with each other (Baumeister et al., 1995). Looking back at human history, we have built technologies that create convenience for us to communicate with each other (Carton, 2019). In modern times, with the advancement of computers, especially with the quick proliferation of social platforms and the usage of snapchat, Instagram or Facebook. The ways of connection between people have changed largely. We are eager to showcase our accomplishments on social platforms, which consequently amplifies our need to live up to the toxic model of being perfect which is nothing more than an insignificant illusion (Wang, 2013).

We see curated content on social media platforms like Facebook or Instagram, all the content or posts are designed in a way to appeal to the viewers and to present an illusion of a perfect life. While looking at those posts we may see that people had a great job, or beautiful homes with a luxury lifestyle, a perfect loving partner, and this may create feelings of jealousy, which make people depressed when they compare it to their lives which may not be that perfect. Social media addiction is relative to depression and similar issues, such as inability to concentrate, sleeping problems, anxiety, and low self-esteem in the youth (Bjomsen & Archer, 2015).

Media addiction can be regarded as an internet addiction type, in which people excessively utilize social media (Starcevic, 2013). The word internet addiction was first time by Ivan Gulberg in 1995 as a psychological illness. Young (1998) regarded it as internet addiction. Martin and 2 Schumacher (2000) stated it as pathological internet use. Studies show that the student and young generation benefits majorly

from social media platforms in general population (Kuss & Griffiths, 2011).

In the 21st century people have access to all information, solving the conflict and self directed learning. When the internet is used as uncontrolled an excessive amount and unconsciously, it can develop anxiety and fear and have aversive effect on personal improvement. Moreover, more use of the internet may have a deteriorating impact on individuals, including domains of psychological, biological, physiological and development of the person in social context using it (Caplan, 2002). Internet addiction was not discussed in the earlier editions; the American Psychiatric Association (APA) regarded internet addiction, with special relationship to online gambling, as a mental disorder to the fifth revision of the Handbook of DSM (APA, 2013).

Theoretical Framework

According to the existing literature, there is an indisputable confederation among media usage and how the results effect the level of mental health and moral values of individuals. However, while the previous literature investigates the connection, it is yet to be explained how these variables are related to one another.

According to the behavioral explanation idea, people utilize social media sites to get benefits like escaping from their reality. According to the social learning theory, behaviors can be generated by seeing and modeling the behaviors of others around you. This idea relates to the learning process and social conduct.

Learning is a cognitive process that takes place in social context and can occur purely through mere observation of others around you even in the absence of direct reinforcement, or direct guidance from someone. In addition to behavioral observation executed by other people, learning is also learned through the observation of rewards and punishments that one receives on a particular task, it is a process known as vicarious reinforcement. This theory states that when individuals see that almost everyone around them is excessively using social media platforms, and is keen to post pictures of themselves and maintain a highly aesthetic wall, people imitate that behavior automatically to social media platforms. This is relevant to the current research as it is very obvious that if a person sees their family using their phones all the time, maybe at the time of lunch or a gathering or even most of the time of the day, so as it is a natural phenomenon that children learn from their parents so they will follow suit and imitate the same pattern of behavior's.

According to cognitive explanation theory, social media addiction is caused as people have faults in their cognitive functioning, and people find using social media as an escape from their internal and external problems of their life. In general, addiction to social media is regarded as a form of cyber- relationship addiction.

This theory states that whenever an individual is going through some issues which may be related to external environment or internal issues, the cognitive process of the individual works in such a way that he finds social media as a means for escape, as when he's indulged in it he is forgetful about his surroundings and for temporary basis he is able to escape from the reality of his life. So, in short, the cognitive explanation theory is related to social media addiction as it's the cognitive functioning or process of an individual which makes people social media as a means of escape from reality. This theory applies to our current researches social media is prevalent to a large extent because people want an escape from their reality, which may be a broken relationship failure at university loss of job or any such thing so to distract their attention they find social media and to run away from the bitter reality of their life, but consequently they make their life more miserable.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A number of researches, indigenously and cross culturally explored the prevalence of social platforms addiction and its effects on moral values and students' mental health at universities. The media addiction and its negative impact on moral values and mental health of teenagers and adults. A huge number of researches have been conducted relative to mental health in Western countries but as a resultant of prevailing behaviors, there is quite a less research on this topic in developing countries such as Pakistan. Lack of awareness and acceptance of mental health issues results in lack of assessment or conversely might be because of a lack of recognition and reporting by the patients. However, there has been a huge increase in reporting of such cases since the 1990s, mental illness is majorly a taboo subject and so the accuracy and authenticity of statistical data needs to be analyzed with caution.

A study was conducted on the prevalence of using social networking sites and developing media addiction among university students in Lahore (Abbas et al., 2020). The study's goal was to determine Instagram usage its addiction level of entertainment and it helps people manage business around the world among teenagers and adults. A survey was conducted and students fill questionnaires. Survey was conducted on university students age 18- 34 years old. Filter questions were asked by the researcher to the respondents before moving to the overarching theme these questions were ask to know about the association of users regarding social networking sites, their endurance, and their intended use. The researcher accepted the individuals' statements that they frequently used Instagram. To get the accurate responses from the respondent's incentives were provided to the users for their time and participation. The participants who does not respond accurately to their questionnaire were excluded. Total 353 participants were selected for data collection Female 27% Male 73% and 84% 18-24 years' old 10% from 25 to 34 years old few participants were undergraduate and some of them had master's degree.

The study results disclose the user optimistic approach towards Instagram had a decided effect on the reliable intention to use social media platform for communication purposes, blogging creating content e-business opportunity and entertainment. A tenable body of data support the right intention to use social networking sites influence the adoption of social networking sites.

A study was conducted on the youth conducted in the University of Sindh and the objective of the study was to recognize the role of social media is to identify the perception of youth about social media and to investigate the collision of media on the construction of the antisocial objective of youth (Abbasi et al., 2021). A quantitative research was conducted on the youth university students age 18- 24 years 42% belief that impact is fair and 38% belief that impact of social media is unfair. Such disparities in beliefs reveal a huge vacuum in research into young perceptions of social media and how they are motivated to use social media to communicate antisocial intent and violent behavior in Pakistan. Participants filled 350 forms out of which 39 were incomplete and 311 students showed up their participation properly. The questions asked in questionnaire was about different social networking sites like WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram etc. The questionnaire consist of 5 parts and analysis of the result was done on SPSS. Results of this study shows the majority 90% of the students use WhatsApp 55.63% of them used Facebook and 37% of the population use Instagram. Therefore, by analyzing the results we can say that our youth is addicted to social media and excess use of social media leads to many problems in youth as it can lead toward violence blackmailing girls and boys sharing inappropriate content can lead to suicide.

A study was conducted to explore the influence of social media on the mental and physical health of university students. It will help us to identify the purpose of using social media (Khalid, 2017). The age range of the students is 16-26 years old and the sample size is 100. The survey was conducted and data was analyzed in SPSS and the results were that students reported they use social media for entertainment purposes 33% of students use Facebook 23% use WhatsApp 21% use YouTube 12% Instagram and 9% Twitter and 2% use other social networks like Snapchat etc. This study also indicates that social media addiction leads to many mental health issues like insomnia, depression, anxiety etc. It has a negative impression on their physical and mental health.

Another study was conducted on social media youth in Pakistan and its associations with family relations. The research was conducted in the University of Islamabad. The objective of the study is to identify the reason for excessive use of social media and excessive use of social media affects family relations (Ali, 2016). This study is conducted by using quantitative method the population sample includes females of age 20-26 175 participants were selected and they were asked to fill the questionnaire and 70% of respondents strongly agreed with the statement that face-to-face interaction was decreased by social networking sites on the question that was asked to the participants was social platforms makes personal relation unreal 42.3% candidate strongly assent 43.4% admit 8.6% of the participants were natural 4.0% were disagreed and 1.7% strongly disagreed.

The study results indicate that social networking sites are in alliance with family relationships and excessive use of social media is making them isolated and lead them to many mental health problems.

A study was administrate in a university to see the effect of social platforms. The objective of the study is to see social networking sites and depression among university students. The Pakistani students participated with the students who use Facebook and Twitter. The age range of the students was from 18- 30 years old (Ahmad, 2018). Quantitative correlational research was conducted Sample of 200 Facebook and Twitter users 132 male participants and 77 female participants. Questionnaire and Beck Depression Inventory was used. The results of this study was that the majority of the male's user were depressed then female. The research findings show that social platforms have negative consequences on the mental state of university students and it leads to depression.

Studies on web addiction, insomnia, and mental health issues among Pakistani university students. The point of this exploration was to research the interceding function of sleep deprivation in the connection between web enslavement and psychological wellbeing issues in college understudies of Pakistan the sample of this research consisted of 1776 university students. Results were demonstrating that sleep deprivation was a huge middle person in the connection between these two web dependence and emotional wellness issues so results were showing that after controlling insomnia internet addiction causes depression so it means insomnia had partial mediation effect (Khalid, 2017).

Throughout the world, different research has been carried out in order to investigate media addiction, mental health and moral values among university students.

A research has been conducted into the relationship between young adult's use of social media and their mental health. The study's goal is to determine whether social media (Berryman et al., 2018) affect young adult's mental health. The University students participated 471 undergraduate students; four members were

excluded due to insufficient data; the last sample size is 467 out of which 335 participants were female and 130 participants were males. The age range of the students was from 19- 27 years. The questions regarding social media were given in questionnaire depression, suicidal thoughts after analyzing the results researcher identified that many aspects of social media on young adults, and on their mental health, it leads them to depression, anxiety suicide and loneliness.

Social media usage can result in harmful behaviors like aggression, certain personality disorders, unhealthy lifestyles and diets, early age sexual behaviors, consumption of tobacco and alcohol in young adults. Consequently, the psychological level of dependence in social interactions builds when this situation is recurrent for the purpose of getting rid of the undesirable mood in social media usage (Hou, 2019).

Another cross-cultural study was conducted to see the addiction of social networking sites. The objective of the study is to see the addiction of Facebook, WhatsApp, Snapchat and Instagram among teenager and adult's researcher wants to find about the time spend on social media user age was from 16-34 years old (Geysler, 2021). Questionnaire are given to participants, different questions were asked regarding different social media sites, and the people gave different responses. Facebook is most visited website 11.2 billion people visited Facebook. People of age 16 to 24 years are mostly Instagram users 37.6% females and 31.2% males. A survey was conducted to see the interest of majority teenage towards different sites and researcher got many different responses 85% of teenager responses were they use YouTube 72% used Instagram 69% used Snapchat and 51% use Facebook. The more they use social media it leads to many mental health problems like stress and depression, which can lead to suicide.

Moreover, social media users are of the view that others have a perfect life and they are happier than them. Looking at the happy photos posted by other people on social media sites and thinking that their lives are always without conflicts, negatively affects their mental state (Sadagheyani & Tatari, 2020). This addiction may cause individuals to escape one's reality of life, mood swings and mental health. The addictive factors of social media have the possibility to contribute as a factor in social media impacts behavior of individuals (Sharma, 2020).

Another study was carried out to check the effects of media addiction on mental state. The goal of this research was to discover the link between social media addiction and depression. The students of university in Istanbul participated age range 18-25 years' old (Haand & Shuwang, 2020). Quantitative method was used 384 undergraduate students participated 55 participants were excluded 9 participants were not using any social networking site 46 incomplete responses final sample was of 329 participants. The male participants were 310 and 19 participants were female. The Cronbach Alpha was above .08 social media addiction and depression. The results show that social media has a relation with mental health and it can lead to depression.

When internet is properly used, it enables the individuals with essential skills for the 21st century such as access of all the information, solving the conflict and self-directed learning. Therefore, when internet is used in an uncontrolled an excessive and unconsciously, it can develop anxiety of fear and have adverse effects on personal improvement (Nakaya, 2015). Moreover, more use of internet may have deteriorating impact on individual including domains of physiological, biological, psychological and development of the person in social contexts using it.

A study was conducted and the objective of the study is to see the social media addiction and mental health during Covid-19 (Guelmami et al., 2021). The number of participants participated in the research were 874 university students participated and

participants age range was 28-32 years' old participants completed the social media addiction scale which consist of 12 items Covid- 19 fear scale has seven items and It was based on a Likert scale with a maximum of five points, ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree, another scale that was use was perceived stress scale which consist of 10 items an online survey was conducted the informed consent was taken the results of the study indicates that the social media addiction scale was appropriate the results shows three factor analysis the first factor explained 45.24% of variance second factor shows 16.70% and third one shows 11.60% which confirms the addiction of social media and its negative effect on mental health.

Social media platforms consume most of the time from our daily chores and activities, we are so engulfed in them that we don't keep the count of hours we are indulged in. It affects our interpersonal relationships with our family and friends which creates a lack of communication between our loved ones. Consequently, the result is that when we feel upset or low or annoyed at something, due to that communication barrier we don't discuss it with our family, and it keeps on building inside us.

If we share something that is bothering us or do our catharsis, we feel much better and it helps in keeping a good mental health. If we take a look at the previous decade, rates of depressive symptoms in people and occurrence of anxiety has increased in the adolescent and younger populations (O'Reilly, 2018). Social media has altered the way younger generations interact with one other in a variety of aspects such as indulging in romance, communicating with friends and organizing social gatherings (Kirik, 2015).

Another study was conducted and the objective of the study was to see the social media addiction and moral values and its relation with pornography and online video gaming (Lewczuk et al., 2021). Social media addiction leads to many problems but it has an negative effect on the moral values and mental health an online study was conducted the age range of participants was 18-25 years old and our results shows that 3.0% of women's and 8.7% of men's agreed that they are addicted to pornography. 23.3% women's and 22.26% of men's agree on interment addiction. 3.0% women's and 5.3% of men's agreed on online gaming detailed frequency of data shows that both men's and women's are addicted to social media but men's us more social media as compare to women's.

Significance of the Study

The research brings to light the fact that social media addiction affects our moral values and mental health. In Pakistan, limited research has been done on the relationship of social media, moral values and mental health. The results of the study are interesting and vent out the doors for the future researchers. The research spotlights the importance of social media addiction impact on mental health and moral values.

METHODOLOGY

The focus of the current study was to investigate the coloration between, media addiction, mental health and moral values among university students.

Research Design

The association between social media addiction, mental health, and moral values among university students was investigated using a correlational research approach.

Ethical Considerations

Research approval was taken from the departmental committee of University of Management and Technology Lahore, as well as from University of Central Punjab, University of Lahore and University of Engineering and Technology. Participants were informed about the purpose of the research, confidentiality and anonymity, and that they could withdraw from the research at any time. Moreover, no incentives were offered to the participants during the research.

Sample and Sampling Strategy

The present study recruited a sample of 200 graduate and undergraduate university students (Male, n= 89, Female, n=111) with age ranging 18-25 years using random sampling technique.

Assessment Measures

Demographic Sheet

A demographic sheet was constructed to collect information regarding age, gender, number of siblings, family system, university, educational level, semester, most used app in social media, daily hours they spent on social media.

Social media addiction scale student form (SMAS-SF)

The Cengiz Sahin for measuring the use of social media addiction scale develops social media addiction scale. This is a 29 item scale based on the theoretical framework. The generated statements intended to capture social media addiction.

Mental health continuum

This scale is 14-item scale developed by the Dr. Keyes in 2009 for the mental health of adult. The scale is uni-dimensional. All item is answered using Likert scale 6-points ranging from never to every day. Its scoring included that the item 1, 2, 3,4,5,6.

The ethics position questionnaire

Bary Schlenker oversaw the scale's development at the University of Florida. Drs. Marvin Shaw, Joel Cohen, Thomas Simon, Larry Servery, William Yost, and R. I. Watson was a member of the committee. The EPQ's inaugural publication was in Forsyth, D.R. (1980). According to the theoretical framework, the scale consists of 20 items.

Data analysis

After data collection, scores were put into Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and statistical analysis was run to analyze data and find results. In the first step descriptive analysis was done to find mean, standard deviation, and reliability of scales. In the second step Individual' ProductMoment Correlation was done to find link between statistic variables with the variable of social media addiction, moral values and mental health. In the third step Hierarchical Regression was done to find predictive values.

The hypothesis of the study were:

H1: There is likely to be a negative relationship between social media addiction and moral values.

H2: There is likely to be a positive relationship between social media addiction and mental health.

H3: There is likely to be a positive relationship between age and high moral values.

H4: Females are likely to be more addicted to social media as compared to males.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Sample (N=200)

Variable	<i>f(%)</i>	<i>M(SD)</i>
Age	-	4.89(1.90)
Gender		-
Male	89(53.2)	-
Female	111(46.8)	-
Family System		-
Joint	64(31.7)	-
Nuclear	136(67.3)	-
University		-
UMT	69(34.2)	-
UCP	53(26.2)	-
UOL	39(19.3)	-
UET	39(19.3)	-
Education		
BS	129(63.9)	
MS	70(34.7)	
Social Media App		
Instagram	66(32.7)	
Facebook	35(17.3)	
WhatsApp	52(25.7)	
Twitter	19(9.4)	

Note *M*=Mean, *SD*=Standard Deviation, *f*=Frequency

Table 1: *Inter-correlations among Social media addiction, Moral Values and Mental Health among University Students (N = 200)*

Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.Age	—	-.23**	.04	.10	.12*	.16*	.13*	.16*
2. Time		—		-.05	-.03	-.05	.01	-.10
3.Social Media Addiction			—				.15*	.23**
							—	.08
4.Mental Health							-.02	-.05
5.Moral Values							—	.91***
6.Idealism								—
7.Relativism								—

Note, *M*=Mean, *SD*=Standard Deviation, *n*=Sample, *T*= Time, *SMA*=Social Media

Addiction, *MH*= Mental Health, *MV*=Moral Values, **p* < .05, ***p* < .01, ****p* < .001
 The outcomes showed that addiction of social media has significant positive correlation with mental health. Social plate forms also have a high correlation-positively with moral values. Moreover, the results shows that there is no relationship between mental health and moral values. Also, the age ha the significant positive relationship with mental health and moral values and its sub scale but no relationship found with social media addiction. While there is no correlation exist between time and social media abdication, mental health and moral values.

Table 2

Hierarchical Multiple Regression Analysis for social media addiction, moral values and mental health (N=200)

Variable	B	95% CI for B		SEB	β	R ²	ΔR^2
		LL	UL				
Step 1						.01	.00
Constant	50.1	44.1	56.0	3.01			
Age	.84	-.12	1.81	.49	.10		
Time spend on social media	-.078	-.363	.207	.14			
Step 2						.03	.02
Constant	40.6	5.70	29.3	51.8			
Age	.74	-.22	1.71	.10	.10		
Time spend on social media	-0.6	-.34	.22	.14	-.03*		
Social Media Addiction	.10	.001	.21	.05	.13		
Step 3						.04	.01
Constant	44.6	31.0	58.32	6.91			
Age	.81	-.16	1.8	.49	.11		
Time spend on social media	-.06	.21	1.80	.14	-.03*		
Idealism	-.05	-1.77	-.89	.08	.05*		
Relativism	-.03	.48	1.34	.10	-.03*		

Note. CI = confidence interval; LL = lower limit; UL = upper limit; SMA = social media addiction **p < .01, ***p < .001. The results shows the moral values is predictor of mental health. In the first step, demographics were added. The explained variance is 0.16% with F (2, 197) 1.58, p<.2. In step two social media addiction was added the variance is 0.19% with F (3,196) = 2.43 p < .05. Whereas social media dedication is the positive predictor of mental health $\beta = .11$ p< 38.2%

Table 3

Variable	Men (n = 89)		Women (n = 111)		t	p	95% CI		Cohen's d
	M	SD	M	SD			LL	UL	
	Social media addiction	92.17	18.17	90.14			16.10	.828	

Mental Health	53.84	13.08	52.96	13.49	.466	191.01	-2.85	4.61	0.06
Moral Values	124.31	24.02	124.32	21.96	.003	180.59	-6.43	6.42	0.00
Idealism	64.97	14.35	65.41	14.04	.218	.828	-4.41	3.54	0.03
Relativism	59.35	12.73	58.92	10.65	.260	.795	-2.83	3.69	0.03

Independent Samples t-test Comparing Study Variables in Men and Women (N=200)

Note. CI = Confidence Interval, LL= Lower Limit, UL = Upper Limit.

The above table shows independent sample t-test, mean and standard deviation of the study variables. Results indicated that there was significant difference among men and women on the basis of social media addiction and moral valued on mental health.

DISCUSSION

The goal of the current study was to explore the bond between social media addiction, moral values and mental health among university students.

The current work stated that addiction of social networking sites is likely to be negatively associated with moral values. The results showed positive link among social media addiction and moral values whereas previous literature showed negative relation between social media addiction and moral values among teenagers and adults. Moral evolution is completely clashing with their religious and cultural norms (Selfridge & Mitchell, 2021). Teenagers and adults using more social media leads them to watch inappropriate content like porn and other stuff like substance abuse which have a negative impact on their moral values 39 (Kim, 2017). The fact that our investigation took place locally with a small group of individuals from a single culture may be the reason for the findings. However, our hypothesis was not supported by any of the results, and said that social media positively predicts moral values among university students. According to a research that was conducted by a researcher in Poland, he gave online surveys to 1036 participants to check out the relationship between social media addiction and moral values the survey was filled by participants including teenagers and adults. The result of the study shows that addiction of media has a negative effect on moral values (Lewczuk et al., 2021). Some other researches that were conducted those researches also shows that social media addiction has a negative effect on the moral values. Previous studies are also shows that there is a negative relation between addiction of social media and moral values. This study was conducted on low level on the minimum sample and mostly on the specific culture which cause difference in the result.

The second hypothesis of the research stated that social media addiction is likely to have a positive bond between addiction of social media and mental health. The multiple hierarchical regression shows that social media is positively linked with mental health. The results showed positive relation between social media addiction and mental health. The purpose of social media is to amplify. By releasing the feel-good chemical dopamine. Using it stimulates the reward area of the brain, which is linked to pleasurable activities like sex, eating, and social interaction. Excess use of social media addiction linked to psychological problems like stress, depression and anxiety. The study was conducted in the United States; social network usage is 81% are teenagers or 69% are adults. According to the Pew Research Center, excess use of

social media is increasing and there is a high possibility that a significant section of the population may suffer from anxiety, depression, or other illnesses as a result of using social media excessively. While previous studies conducted at national and worldwide levels, with large numbers of participants from a variety of cultures, norms, and beliefs system. Our study conducted at a local level with a small number of participants from a single culture, which may be the cause of positive results (Mitchell, 2021) .However, all results indicate and predict a positive relationship; therefore, the study hypothesis not supported, and it can be conclude that social media had positive results on our mental health among university students.

The third hypothesis of the current study stated that age and moral values has positive relationship between them the results showed significant positive relation between Age and moral values. Moral development in children begins at birth and progresses over time, as they get older. A child brain is a “blank slate” (Kristie, 2014). Child will learn whatever he will be taught, observe ideas and beliefs change from time to time with the experience but some beliefs are rigid and cannot be changed easily. Researches and theories also support our hypothesis “The Kohlberg theory of moral development” the focus of this theory was on the children moral development. According to theory, Children's moral development begins in childhood and continues until the adulthood. Every level of the theory has it importance with the passage of time, any kind of conflict can cause negative effect on the moral development (Walker, 1982).

A research was conducted in Italy on school children of grade four, seven and tenth participated children belong to different socio-economic status and different ages participated in the study there were total 21 items in the scale and they have to respond to the question they have to judge it is morally right or wrong(Caravita,2017). The results of the study showed that every group responded well except few. Hence, our results also support the hypothesis and it is partially accepted.

The forth hypothesis showed that females use more social networking sites as compared to males. The results also showed the non-significant relation between males and females, whereas previous literature also support that excessive use of twitter is effecting individuals social life's adversely (Ndasauka, 2016). Previous research revealed that gender differences and personal traits might both play important roles in addictive behavior. An examination of male and female college students from a cross-sectional perspective sample of 278 participants was used. Furthermore, the many surveys used the Social Network Addiction Questionnaire. The results showed that many survey, social media addicts of both sexes are distinct from oneanother. The study showed that social network addiction might be influenced by gender, with socio-psychological aspects in women's are being more significant than the men's are, which combine biological and social elements. However, all results indicate and predict that nonsignificant relationship among males and females addiction. Therefore, our results do not support the hypothesis and it can be conclude that both females and males are equally addicted to the social media.

CONCLUDING RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concluded that social media addiction and moral values have positive relationship with each other. Social media addiction or mental health had a positive relationship with each other. Moral value was found to have a relationship with the Age. Moreover, NO significant difference of Social Media Addiction between Females and Males are showed. Social networking sites provides individual with constant exposure to upward social comparison, which cause envy, depression, social

anxiety in the individuals, they compare their restricted life with the online perfected versions and develop envious feelings and other psychological problems.

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Ethics and Permission

The present study was approved by the Department Research Ethics Committee from Universities.

Author Contributions Statement

Ansa Liaqat conceptualized and conducted the study under the supervision of Muhammad Atif Rasool. All the authors drafted and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Data sharing and availability statement

Data is available from the corresponding author based on request.

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